

FUNCTIONING OF DENTAL PRACTICES IN A COMPLICATED EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION

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ABSTRACT

The COVID pandemic and the global economic crisis have had a profound impact on the organization, functioning, economic well-being, and professional prospects of dental practices, as well as on the dental health of patients in Bulgaria. In the first months of the COVID pandemic, dental practices faced the difficult task of obtaining scarce personal protection equipment (masks, gloves, overalls, safety goggles, etc.) In addition to their lack, the price at which they could be purchased was also a problem. Dental professionals report a reduced flow of patients for prophylaxis and standard manipulations.

Keywords: dental practices, patients, dental health, COVID pandemic.

At the beginning of the pandemic, one of the main problems was the lack of information about the pathogen - clinical picture, mode of spread, ways to protect, and treatment. For several months, this information was selected by scientists and doctors around the world. The scientific and clinical data on the COVID pandemic are being updated, supplemented, and analyzed to this day. Based on this scientific information, guidelines are being created to prevent infection with the virus, methods to limit the spread of the infection, treatment regimens for the disease, vaccines, and pharmaceutical treatments are being developed.

Impact of the COVID pandemic on dental practices

In relation to the topic, a survey was conducted using a direct anonymous survey method. Data were collected online, using Google forms for the period 2020 -

2021. The sample was typological, collecting data on patients, and dentists. Descriptive and analytical statistical methods were applied: data are presented as absolute numbers and relative share of each category, and age (the only quantitative variable in the survey) as mean and standard deviation. Of the analytical statistics methods, chi-square analysis was applied. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant.

Results:

Data were collected on 206 patients and 193 dentists (dental practitioners). The sample as a whole was predominantly female (77.4%), and this was also true for each of the study groups (71.0% among dentists, and 83.5% among patients). The study subjects were 46.3 years old on average. Table 1.

Table 1.

General characteristics of respondents

Variables		Total		Dentists		Patients	
		N	%	n	%	n	%
Gender	Male	90	22,6%	56	29,0%	34	16,5%
	Female	309	77,4%	137	71,0%	172	83,5%
Age (arithmetic mean±SD)		46,3±11,2		46,0±11,6		46,4±11,0	

Dental practices have been affected by the COVID pandemic in several ways that have had a major impact on their economic status and active functioning. As initially reported, the problem was the lack of information about the pathogen, its spread, methods of prevention, as well as the clinical picture of the disease, and, above all, the lack of clearly defined treatment rules. The many unknowns, as well as the strict restrictive measures that were initially introduced by the government, have led to the closure of a huge number of dental practices. Dental practices were therefore deprived of their profits.

Dentists were asked if they had suspended their activities since the beginning of the COVID pandemic. Over half reported that this had happened to them (59.6%), while the remaining 40.4% had not stopped working. The highest proportion of those who stopped at the beginning, when the state of emergency was declared (86.2%), followed by those who stopped their activities for the duration of their illness or quarantine (6.9%), and another 5.2% stopped during the peak of the epidemic. A further 1.7% reported working according to a reduced schedule almost every month. The survey showed that due to the COVID epidemic, dentists experienced a decrease in patients, with more than half

of dentists (55.6%) reporting this (Table 2). The reduction in patients during the peak of the epidemic was reported by 65.4% of dentists.

The fact that the virus initially attacks and develops in the nasopharynx makes the dentist's work particularly risky. The patient is infectious both during the incubation period - when there are no symptoms - and after he develops a clinical picture of the disease. As highlighted, this makes the working environment of dentists highly risky. Therefore, some dentists - most often older and/or with co-morbidities - severely restrict or stop seeing patients. These actions, driven by concern for their health, lead to financial losses for the dental practices they run.

In everyday dental practice, rotary instruments are continuously used, which, when working in the oral cavity, lead to the swirling of an air-aerosol cloud. If the patient is positive and is a carrier of a COVID infection, viral particles are also swirled in this air-aerosol cloud. Therefore, to reduce the risk of infection and subsequent illness of the dentist and the support team of dental assistants, hygienists, and receptionists in the dental surgery, it is recommended:

1. To use protective clothing, safety masks with the maximum degree of protection, safety glasses with side shields, safety helmets, safety gloves, and shoe covers.
 2. To ventilate the dental surgery
 3. To disinfect the workplace and the surgery
 4. To conduct triage - the dentist takes a history of the patient to report the absence or presence of symptoms for COVID infection (presence or absence of fever, headache, night sweats, scanty running nose, sore throat, conjunctivitis, muscle pain, loss of sense of smell, cough, contact with people sick with COVID)
 5. Availability of a green certificate (vaccine, previous illness, antigen test, PCR)
 6. To conduct a rapid antigen test in dental surgery.
 7. To enrol patients with time off in between.
- Thus, on the one hand, the aim is that the patients do not meet each other in the waiting room as a preventive measure against COVID infection. On the other hand, this ensures the necessary time for cleaning, disinfection, and ventilation of the workplace and work area. These free time intervals between patients are recommended to be in the order of 15-20 min.

Concerning the protective equipment used in the work in the period before the start of the COVID pandemic, dentists were expected to use more and more

varied equipment due to the specific nature of their work. Almost all dentists (97.4%) used a mask; gloves were applied in the practice of almost all dentists (95.9%); protective goggles were used by 75.6% of dentists; protective overalls were used by 14.5% of dentists, bonnets by 22.3% of dentists, and something else by 10.9% of dentists. Helmets, air purifiers, and disposable clothes/towels were the most frequently mentioned in the "other" response. The percentages added up to more than 100 as respondents gave more than one answer. It is possible that some respondents misunderstood the question and answered with the time since the pandemic began in mind.

The dentists surveyed were asked what new precautions they had added since the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic began. A quarter of dentists (26.4%) reported that they had not supplemented their practice with a new means of protection. A mask was added by 25.6% of dentists; gloves were added by 22.3%; protective eyewear was started by 31.1%; overalls by 42.5%; bonnet by 35.8% and something else by 12.4%. In the "other" response, helmets, air purifiers, disposable sheets/clothes, and higher-grade masks (FFP2) were the most common. The percentages sum to more than 100 as respondents gave more than one answer. It is possible that some respondents who were confused by the previous question did not write down the additional protective equipment after the start of the COVID epidemic, as they had already noted them in the previous question.

The majority of dentists responded positively to the question "Do you spend more time per patient appointment to further clean and disinfect the surgery?", 84.5% respectively. The proportion of negative responses was 9.3% and those who could not judge were 6.2%, respectively.

Dentists were asked if they book patients at greater intervals to ensure that patients do not meet in the waiting room for their surgery. The majority of respondents answered in the affirmative: 76.7%, while the remaining 23.3% did not take such a measure.

More than two-thirds of the dentists (70.5%) questioned all their patients about their current health status to identify symptoms of COVID among them. Only at-risk groups are asked by 10.4% of dentists. 17.6% of dentists do not collect such information. Three dentists responded with "other", and their responses indicate that this was an activity they performed at the beginning of the pandemic, but they do not collect such information recently.

Table 2.

Variables		Total		Dentists	
		n	%	n	%
Has the COVID pandemic affected the number of patients visiting your surgery?	Yes, they decreased	114	55,6%	110	57,0%
	No	50	24,4%	48	24,9%
	Yes, they grew	19	9,3%	16	8,3%
	I can not judge	22	10,7%	19	9,8%
Do you notice a noticeable change in the number of patients visiting your surgery related to the peak of the pandemic?	Yes, patients decrease during COVID peaks	134	65,4%	128	66,3%
	No	40	19,5%	40	20,7%
	Yes, patients increase during COVID peaks	9	4,4%	7	3,6%
	I can not judge	22	10,7%	18	9,3%
What personal protective equipment did you use in your practice before the COVID pandemic	I have not used	1	0,5%	0	0,0%
	Mask	199	97,1%	188	97,4%
	Gloves	195	95,1%	185	95,9%
	Safety glasses	153	74,6%	146	75,6%
	Safety overalls	30	14,6%	28	14,5%
	Safety Bonnet	45	22,0%	43	22,3%
	Other	22	10,7%	21	10,9%
	Answer "Other"	Helmet	16		15
	Air Purifier	1		1	
	Disposable clothes/sheets	4		4	
	All that exists as protection!	1		1	
What personal protection equipment have you added to your practice since the start of the COVID pandemic	I have not added a new protection	52	25,4%	51	26,4%
	Mask	54	26,3%	49	25,4%
	Gloves	49	23,9%	43	22,3%
	Safety glasses	63	30,7%	60	31,1%
	Safety overalls	85	41,5%	82	42,5%
	Safety bonnet	71	34,6%	69	35,8%
	Other	25	12,2%	24	12,4%
Answer "Other"	Helmet	15		14	
	Air Purifier	5		5	
	Disposable clothes/sheets	4		4	
	Higher class mask (ffp2)	1		1	
Do you take more time to see one patient to further clean and disinfect the surgery	Yes	173	84,4%	163	84,5%
	No	19	9,3%	18	9,3%
	I can not judge	13	6,3%	12	6,2%
When patients come to your surgery, do you collect information about their current health status to detect symptoms of COVID	Yes, for every patient	142	69,3%	136	70,5%
	Yes, for patients from risk groups	25	12,2%	20	10,4%
	No	35	17,1%	34	17,6%
	Other	3	1,5%	3	1,6%
How is the pandemic affecting the general/dental health of your patients?	Negative	138	67,3%	128	66,3%
	No reflection	65	31,7%	63	32,6%
	Positive	2	1,0%	2	1,0%
During the COVID pandemic, what patients with what need visit your dental surgery	Patients with pain in need of emergency dental care			151	78,2%
	Patients in need of standard manipulations - therapeutic, surgical, periodontal, etc.			171	88,6%
	Aesthetic procedures			53	27,5%
	Other			2	1,0%
Have you suspended your dental practice at any time during the pandemic	Yes			115	59,6%
	No			78	40,4%
Did you stop your dental practice at any time during the pandemic - when	in the beginning, when the state of emergency was declared			100	86,2%
	at epidemic peaks			6	5,2%
	during your illness/quarantine			8	6,9%
	I work at a reduced schedule almost every month			2	1,7%
Do you enroll patients at greater intervals as an anti-epidemic measure so that patients do not meet each other in the waiting room	Yes			148	76,7%
	No			45	23,3%

All these protective equipment, disinfectants as well as the additional time for ventilation, cleaning, disinfection, preventing patients from meeting each other in the waiting room, and conducting a rapid antigen test if there is no green certificate, make the treatment process more expensive and if they are at the expense of the dental practice reduce its financial income, and if they are calculated in the cost of dental treatment lead to the increase in the cost of the dental procedures and are at the expense of patients. If in the first case, we have increased costs that lead to a direct reduction in the dental practice's income, in the second case the increase in the cost of dental procedures leads to a partial outflow of patients, which indirectly has a negative impact on the dental practice's financial income.

Another problem of dental practices related to the COVID pandemic is the supply of dental consumables and materials. In the initial stages of the spread of infection, the supply of protective equipment was extremely difficult to obtain and at speculatively inflated prices. At present, the supply of protective equipment is unproblematic but due to the COVID pandemic on the one hand, the difficulties in the supply of raw materials and electricity on the other hand, and international and national inflationary processes, significant price increases between 50% and 150%, sometimes more, are currently being reported. There are also shortages or severely delayed supplies of some standard dental materials, and here too sustained price increases of 40% or more are being observed. The lack of some materials and/or their increased prices lead to their substitution by others, which on the one hand can worsen the quality of the treatment process and on the other hand when they are replaced by more expensive raw materials, as well as increased prices of personal protective equipment, can make the whole complex of dental manipulations more expensive. Unfortunately, this price increase has a negative impact on some patients, who reduce the number of dental treatments they can pay for or visit dental surgeries offering dental services at lower prices. In the latter situation, the lower price in most cases manifests itself as unsatisfactory quality, which in the long term is again a negative aspect for the patient. The lower financial receipts in the dental surgeries lead to a limitation of cash for the purchase of new materials, updating of the material base of the surgery, and training of the staff, in some cases a reduction of staff is necessary, which again affects the quality of the treatment offered.

Some of the dental practices have used loans and the financial instability caused by the COVID pandemic is leading to the danger of their closure. This is on the one hand a financial problem for the employed staff who are left without a job, a problem for the state social security as the employees register at the unemployment bureau, and a problem for the patients who are faced with the choice of a new dentist and above all a difficult time from a financial and psychological point of view for the owners of dental practices.

Another economic problem indirectly linked to the COVID pandemic is the significant increase in the price of electricity and gas supplies internationally. In Bulgaria, unlike domestic electricity consumers, who use electricity for domestic purposes at a price that is currently limited by a moratorium, dental surgeries, and general practitioners' practices use industrial electricity, which is traded on the free electricity market and is at exchange prices. Many dental practices are subscribers to district heating companies, which is a major cost and high expense.

Dentists in their daily practice use the services of dental technicians. There has been an increase in the prices of dental technician services, which again is indirectly linked to the COVID pandemic and the international chaos it has caused, inflation - international and national, expensive electricity, and difficulty in supplying internationally expensive materials.

Dentistry is a specialty, which is actively developing and is closely related to technical progress. Seminars, training, and professional exhibitions are mandatory parts of the professional development and growth of dentists. In the course of the COVID pandemic and to comply with the anti-epidemic measures, dentists' training has been severely affected.

Impact of the COVID pandemic on patients' dental health

One of the most interesting questions in the survey was "How is the pandemic affecting the dental health of your patients?". Dentists reporting a negative effect resulting from the pandemic were 66.3%. Only two dentists (1%) believe the pandemic is having a positive impact. According to another 32.6% of dentists, the COVID pandemic has had no impact on their patients' overall health.

Dentists were asked what patients who visited their surgeries during the pandemic were suffering from. The highest proportion reported that patients needed standard manipulations (88.6%), but a relatively high proportion also reported that patients came in with pain needing emergency dental care (78.2%). Something else was indicated by another 1%, adding that it was "anything" and long-delayed treatment that was urgent". The percentages added up to more than 100 as participants gave more than one answer.

Among the patients surveyed, the most commonly reported reason for going to the dentist was tooth decay (38.3%), followed by having a crown, bridge, or denture made or replaced (23.3%), a broken tooth (13.6%), cosmetic dentistry (11.2%), tooth extraction (9.2%), tooth pain (0.5%), or something else (14.6%). Among the "other" responses, preventive check-ups predominated, followed by tartar cleaning. The sum of the percentages exceeded 100 as respondents gave more than one answer.

We examined whether there was a difference between dentists' and patients' responses regarding reasons for visiting dental surgery.

Fig. 1.

Differences in patients' and dentists' responses regarding the reasons that led them to visit dental surgeries.

There was a significant difference in the proportion of physicians and patients reporting a pain visit, $p < 0.001$. There was no significant difference in the responses of dentists and patients who reported a visit for standard, aesthetic, and other manipulations ($p > 0.05$).

In the survey, patients were asked about the frequency of dental surgery visits before the COVID epidemic. More than one-third responded at least once a year (37.9%) and at least twice a year (36.9%), while the remaining 25.2% went to the dentist only for emergencies/pain.

For the majority of patients (60.5%), the COVID epidemic did not affect the number of visits to dental

surgery but one in three (33.2%) reported that the number had decreased, in 0.5% (one patient) it had increased, and another 5.9% could not judge.

Patients who visited a dental surgery for various reasons since the beginning of the COVID epidemic were 79.1%, while 20.9% did not.

Differences were sought in dentists' and patients' responses to the questions "Has the COVID pandemic affected the number of patients visiting your surgery?" (for dentists) and "Has the COVID pandemic affected your standard number of dental surgery visits on an annual basis?" (for patients). The two groups were shown to respond differently, with differences persisting even when eliminating the "can't judge" response, $p < 0.01$.

FIG. 2. Impact of the COVID pandemic on dental surgery visits according to patients and dentists

A possible explanation for this imbalance in responses between patients and dentists is that the survey was taken by patients who on the one hand were proactive in general life and on the other hand were responsible for their general and in particular their dental health. For them, the number of visits to dental surgery on an annual basis has remained virtually unchanged despite the pandemic. A large proportion of these patients visit the same dental practice for many years. They are satisfied with the services offered and have

faith in the work of the dentist as well as the sterilization and disinfection carried out in the practice. These are patients with well-maintained oral health and usually need standard dental manipulations that are not emergencies. On the other hand, dental practices are also visited by patients who are irresponsible with their dental health and it can be assumed that the COVID pandemic has reinforced this irresponsibility, which according to dentists has manifested itself in a decrease in the total number of patients visiting dental practices and an increase in pain emergencies.

Fig. 3. Differences in responses of patients and dentists regarding the intensity of dental treatment during the COVID pandemic.

Because the mean values of patients according to their answers to the question "Has the COVID pandemic affected your standard number of dental surgery visits per year?" varied, patients were divided into 4 groups according to their age, in 15-year intervals.

Table 4.

Age markers of dental surgery visits during the COVID pandemic.

Your age

Has the COVID pandemic affected your standard number of dental surgery visits per year?	Arithmetic mean	n	Standard deviation
Yes, they decreased	49,1	68	10,8
No	44,7	124	10,6
Yes, they increased	37,0	1	.
I can not judge	49,3	12	14,0
Total	46,4	205	11,0

Due to the small number of patients in the individual responses ("yes, increased" and "can't judge"), they were excluded from the analysis because they violated the conditions for its application (number of expected frequencies in cells above 5). Different age groups were shown to respond significantly differently to this question, $p=0.013$: as age increased, more patients reported that the number of visits to dental surgery decreased.

Fig. 4. Patients' responses regarding their perceived risk of COVID when visiting the dentist and physician and age comparability of the problem.

Patients were asked if they considered it risky to visit their dentist. 35.0% and 48.5%, respectively, rated going to the dentist as risky; for 48.5%, going to the dentist was not risky. 16.5% could not judge their dentist appointment (Table 3).

Tab. 3.

Patient responses			
Variables		n	%
In your opinion, is it risky to visit the dentist because of the COVID pandemic?	Yes	72	35,0%
	No	100	48,5%
	I can not judge	34	16,5%
How often did you visit the dentist before the COVID pandemic (March 2020)	Only if necessary (emergency/pain)	52	25,2%
	At least once a year	78	37,9%
	At least twice a year	76	36,9%
Has the COVID pandemic affected your standard number of dental surgery visits per year?	Yes, they decreased	68	33,2%
	No	124	60,5%
	Yes, they increased	1	,5%
Have you visited a dentist since the beginning of the COVID pandemic (March 2020)	Yes	163	79,1%
	No	43	20,9%
	On what occasion did you visit the dental surgery during a pandemic	Pain in a tooth	1
Caries		79	38,3%
Broken tooth		28	13,6%
Tooth extraction		19	9,2%
Making or replacement of crowns, bridges, dentures		48	23,3%
Aesthetic dentistry		23	11,2%
Other		30	14,6%
Answer "Other"	Prophylactic examination	17	
	Cleaning tartar	7	
	Other	6	

Some patients, mostly the elderly, are embarrassed to visit dental surgery because of their fear of COVID infection. Patients are found to miss their regular annual check-ups. This leads to undiagnosed problems in the meantime, aggravating them medically and making them more expensive financially. It is reported that there are patients who started treatment before the COVID pandemic but did not complete it or interrupted it. Subsequently, the interruption of the treatment led to a worsening of the clinical findings in the oral cavity and a corresponding change in the treatment plan. An

increased percentage of periodontal disease was found. The explanation on the one hand is the patient's fear of COVID infection and consequently not coming to the dental surgery for a prophylactic examination and professional oral hygiene. On the other hand, it was found that when working online, at home, patients significantly underestimated their oral hygiene, and when a prophylactic examination was performed on patients who had impeccable hygiene and healthy periodontal health, the absence of plaque, gingival inflammation,

and presence of dental plaque was found. This is indicative of neglected personal oral hygiene at home and leads to the development of caries and its complications at a later stage besides periodontal disease. During the peaks of the different waves of the COVID pandemic, there was a decrease in patients visiting dental surgeries. At these times, the patients who visit dental surgeries most often present with an acute dental problem accompanied by pain.

In some patients, there is a temporary postponement of restorative dental manipulations that are not characterized by urgency. This postponement is on the one hand due to the fear of COVID infection, on the other hand to financial problems caused indirectly by the COVID pandemic, and thirdly to the lack of vaccination certificates at the moment.

Because they have not sought dental care because of concerns about COVID infection, some patients complain of gastrointestinal problems caused by poor mechanical processing in the oral cavity. Patients with uncontrolled diabetes due to lack of examination by an

endocrinologist are found to have periodontal problems.

Before the availability of vaccines, some patients had expressed concern about infecting their elderly relatives and therefore refrained from visiting the dentist. With the advent of vaccines in the fight against the COVID pandemic, the worries of infecting both dentists and patients have diminished.

It is interesting to see the difference between doctors' and patients' responses regarding dental health. It turns out that the two groups (doctors and patients) have different opinions about the impact of the pandemic on people's dental health: the proportion of those who think the impact is negative is similar, 67.3% of doctors and 61.2% of patients, respectively. The percentage of individuals believing that the pandemic had no impact was significantly higher among physicians (31.2%) than among patients (19.7). In contrast, only 1% of physicians and as many as 19.1% of patients expressed the opinion that the COVID pandemic had positively affected their health. The differences were significant, with $p < 0.001$

Fig. 4. Distribution of responses to the question "How has the COVID pandemic affected dental health" by respondent type (relative proportion of responses for the respective respondent type)

Conclusion:

In dental offices, the patient flow, the standard course of dental treatment as well as the financial revenues are seriously affected by the COVID pandemic in several ways.

1. Dentists perform treatment activities in a high-risk environment where the likelihood of a COVID infection is significant. As a precautionary measure for dental professionals and their teams, in addition to personal protective equipment, strict disinfection, ventilation, the use of UV lamps, and buffer periods of free time between patients, vaccination is recommended as the method of protection of the highest importance.

2. As a result of the COVID pandemic, the financial profits of dental practices have fallen due to a reduction in patient flow (patients who have fallen ill, patients worried about the risk of infection, patients without a green certificate, patients declaring an inability to currently pay the increased prices of dental services).

3. Difficulties in the standard treatment process due to lack or delayed supply of certain dental consumables and materials and their replacement with analogues, which affects the quality and pricing of treatment procedures.

4. Increasing costs of dental clinics based on expensive electricity, increased prices of dental consumables and materials, more time spent on cleaning, ventilation, disinfection - chemical and physical with (UV lamps), additional finances for the purchase of personal protective equipment, increased prices of dental services, etc.

As a result of the COVID pandemic, patients have seen their dental health deteriorate due to a lack of regular preventive check-ups. Also, a worsening of existing pathologies is reported again due to a lack of timely dental care. For some patients, the problem lies in their fear of infection, while for others, the increased cost of dental services appears to be an insurmountable obstacle at present.

References

1. D. Shopov, Ts. Petrova-Gotova, T. Stoeva. Analysis of health service rendering in the primary and specialized outpatient medical aid in the Republic of Bulgaria, *General Medicine*, 2021, 23 (2): 14-19
2. D. Shtereva-Tzouni, V. Mitreva, E. Naseva. THE IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON THE FUNCTIONING OF DENTAL PRACTICES AND THE GENERAL HEALTH OF PATIENTS IN BULGARIA, *General Medicine* 2022, 24(3), pp. 3–10
3. Li L, Zeng M, Chen X, Cai S, Xu C, Xia W, Jiang L, Zou X, Chen P and Rong M (2021) Optimizing Safe Dental Practice During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Recommendations Based on a Guide Developed for Dental Practices in China. *Front. Med.* 8:619357. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2021.619357
4. T. Zlatanova, M. Djuglarska, N. Popov, D. Shtereva-Tzouni, Ts. Petrova-Gotova, R. Yaneva, E. Naseva, M. Lazarova, Ts. Stoyanova, N. Popov. The regulation by the nhif in the context of covid-19 in opinion of general practitioners, *General Medicine* 2022, 24 (6), pp. 26-35
5. Vodenitcharova AI. The new style of leadership management in the Healthcare system, Sofia, 2016, 229.
6. www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/covid-teeth - 06.2022 г.
7. www.mh.government.bg/bg/covid-19/ - 10.2022 г.
8. www.psnet.ahrq.gov/primer/covid-19-and-dentistry-challenges-and-opportunities-providing-safe-care# - 11.2022 г.
9. www.england.nhs.uk/coronavirus/primary-care/dental-practice/ - 09.2022 г.

PHYSICAL THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF FACIAL NERVE NEUROPATHY

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to studying the effectiveness of physical therapy in the treatment of facial nerve neuropathy.

Keywords: facial nerve neuropathy, physical therapy, massage, ultrasound, electrical stimulation, facial muscle paralysis, quality of life, treatment.

Problem statement.

The facial nerve (Latin: nervus facialis) provides innervation to all the facial muscles, the stapedius muscle of the middle ear, most exocrine glands of the head (except for the parotid glands), including the tear glands, nasal and oral mucosa glands. This structure also functions as a taste receptor for the anterior two-thirds of the tongue and provides sensitivity to a small area of the ear [3]. Bell's palsy is the result of damage to the facial nerve, which can be caused by frequent exposure to cold, infections, intoxications, or trauma. This condition was first described in 1836 by Scottish physiologist Charles Bell, and it was named after him. Bell's palsy is accompanied by serious physical and psychological problems such as facial asymmetry, drooling, and other symptoms that can affect the patient's social activity [12]. Facial nerve neuritis is an inflammatory lesion of the nerve that innervates the facial muscles on one side of the face [4]. As a result, weakness develops in the muscles, leading to a decrease (paresis) or complete absence (paralysis) of facial movements and causing facial asymmetry.

Facial nerve neuritis is the most common among cranial nerve disorders in children [5], while in adults, it ranks second among cranial nerve disorders. The prevalence of this condition among children is explained by the anatomical features of the facial nerve [5]: 1) in children, the fallopian canal is not yet fully formed, so the facial nerve exits practically under the

skin from the temporal bone, increasing the risk of injury compared to adults; 2) the nipple-like projection of the temporal bone is also not fully formed in children, making this nerve less protected from injury.

Currently, viruses are believed to play an important role in the development of facial nerve neuritis. Studies in recent years have shown that patients with this disease have increased titers of antibodies to viruses such as herpes simplex, Epstein-Barr, influenza, and adenoviruses in their blood. Neuritis often occurs as a result of hypothermia [4]. For a long time, the pathogenesis of facial neuropathy was explained by various theories, including vascular, inflammatory, and others [6]. Nowadays, facial neuropathy is considered as one of the variants of a tunnel syndrome. Recent studies confirm the sequence of changes that occur with this disease, namely: "ischemia, edema, compression" or "primary ischemia, edema, compression, secondary ischemia". The development of inflammation and edema leads to compression and ischemia of the facial nerve. Prolonged and pronounced compression of the nerve can result in demyelination and secondary degeneration of nerve fibers [5; 4; 11].

Clinical manifestations of facial nerve neuropathy depend on the level of nerve damage. The main clinical symptom is paresis or paralysis of the facial muscles on the corresponding side of the face, leading to facial asymmetry. In addition, ophthalmological symptoms such as inability to close the eye due to paralysis of the